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EDDU Protocols

Induction of Dopaminergic Neuronal Progenitors From iPSCs Using Microfabricated Disk

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

This protocol describes how to generate dopaminergic neural progenitor cells (DPCs) from induced-pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) using microfabricated embryoid body disk device (EB disk) (**Figure 1**).

This protocol describes how to:

- Thaw and culture dopaminergic neural progenitor cells (DPCs).
- Plate DPCs in a 96 well format to be differentiated into dopaminergic neurons (DNs).

Note: We will be referring to dopaminergic neural progenitor cells as DPCs. On our previous protocols ([EDDU004](#) and [EDDU008](#)) these cells were referred as DA NPCs.

1.2 Protocol overview

Advantages for using this method to generate embryoid bodies (EBs) include but are not limited to:

- Easy to use: workflow for generating large numbers of EBs
- Reproducible: large numbers of uniform EBs ~948 EBs
- Consistency: reduces variability in differentiation protocols.

[In our earlier SOP](#), we used conventional EB formation methods to generate DPCs from iPSC. Through this approach, iPSCs can be aggregated spontaneously, meaning the number of cells incorporated into each aggregate often varies. Thus, the number and size of EBs that form depends on the probability that the cells encounter each other accidentally. Consequently, the size and shape of the resulting EBs tend to be heterogeneous.

The presence of EBs of heterogeneous sizes directly affects subsequent differentiation trajectories, leading to inefficient and uncontrolled differentiation. With this in mind, it is necessary to form EBs in a uniform and reproducible manner with regulated homogeneity in morphology and differentiation status. Here we describe an easy and standardized approach to produce uniform EBs with the use of microfabricated EB disks.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S104620232100195X?via%3Dihub>). Each disk contains 948 defined size microwells, making it possible to produce large amounts of homogenous EBs, ensuring enhanced reproducibility in progenitors and neurons that are differentiated.

By using a combination of small molecules that regulate dual SMAD and floorplate-based signalling pathways, we adapted an existing method to guide iPSCs towards DPCs, that can subsequently be guided into DNs (**Figure 2**).

iPSC cultures are first dissociated into single cells and then cultured in suspension within the EB disks to generate >800–900 uniform EBs. These EBs are re-plated and differentiated into neural rosettes which are subsequently differentiated into DPCs.

DPCs are then seeded into 96-well plates and differentiated into an enriched population of mature DNs after 4 to 6 weeks in culture.

Figure 1. Microfabricated EB-Disk 948 device with 948 microwells. The left picture represents a general view of the EB-Disk 948 in a dish. Scale bar = 10 mm. The middle top view displays the well array. Scale bar = 3 mm. The side middle view, from a cut disk shows the structure of the microwells. Scale bar=1 mm. The right picture shows the flexibility of the disk. From Nguyen-Vi M. et al., *Methods*, 2021.

Figure 2. Protocol overview for the generation of DPCs from iPSCs via EB suspension culture using an EB-Disk.

DPC induction may be performed over two or three weeks, depending on the maturation of the neuronal progenitors. Typically, the induction is performed over two weeks, resulting in a culture of immature progenitors or a mixed cell population. To generate a more mature population of progenitors that are closer to resembling a neuronal precursor phenotype and that can be differentiated into DNs faster, the induction period is extended to three weeks. The additional week of culturing in induction media improves cell proliferation and more readily differentiates them into neurons. Regardless of whether induction is performed over two or three weeks, the first passage of the culture from induction media into NPC media is identified as P0. The cells may next be expanded by passaging at one-week intervals (P1, P2, etc.), frozen down, or differentiated into final neurons. In this protocol, we describe the three week-induction approach (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Timeline of a three-week induction protocol. Following induction, cultures are passaged at one-week intervals.

DPCs can be further differentiated into an enriched population of functionally mature DNs (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Protocol overview for the differentiation of DNs in 96-well plates from DPCs.

1.3 Technical and safety considerations

The following information should be read before starting:

- Refer to [EDDU-001-01](#) for information on preparation and storage conditions for reagents used in cell culture.
- Refer to [EDDU-016-01](#) for information on the usage of EL406 Washer Dispenser.
- All cells must be handled within a Class II biosafety laminar flow hood to protect the worker from possible adventitious agents. McGill University Environmental Health and Safety (EHS) office regulations must be followed.
- High-quality iPSCs are essential for induction of DPCs. iPSCs should be recovered from a frozen stock and passaged at least twice before using in this protocol. *To learn more please read our [iPSC protocol](#) and our [iPSC quality control paper](#).*

Work with one cell line at a time to avoid errors and having to leave cells unattended for too long during procedures.

- Take extra precautions to maintain sterility:
 - Aspirate media using a 1000- μ L tip on top of a 1-mL plastic serological pipette and change to a new tip frequently to avoid cross-contamination.
- Manipulate cells gently:
 - Add and aspirate media to vessels slowly and resuspend cells slowly. If possible, avoid adding media directly onto cells (e.g., dispense media onto the upper interior surface of the flask or onto the side of the plate well).
 - Mix cells in a tube by pipetting slowly a few times or by gently inverting. Do not over-pipette cells.
- Maintain a stable culture environment for cells during incubation:
 - Culture vessels should be placed toward the back of the cell culture incubator shelf to maintain stable temperature and CO₂ levels when the door of the incubator is opened and closed.
 - When dissociating cells, use a different 37 °C incubator than the cell culture incubator to minimize opening and closing the door of the cell culture incubator. Note that the dissociation incubator should be sterile but does not require a CO₂ supply.
- When manipulating the EB-Disk please follow the instructions below:
 - Do not aspirate directly from the wells of the EB-Disk. Aspirate from a corner of the dish instead.
 - When filling the disk with media, press the disk down into the dish with sterile forceps to make sure the wells get filled.
 - To not disturb the EBs being formed in the microwells avoid tilting the dishes at all times.
 - EBs cultures consist of cell aggregates. Use a 10-mL glass pipette during resuspension and transfer of EB cultures to minimize breakage of cell aggregates.

– EBs must be transferred to Matrigel-coated T25 flask for Rosette formation.

Some of these steps can be visualized on our [EB-disk protocol instructional video](#).

- DPCs may be recovered from a frozen stock or generated from iPSCs.
 - DPCs and neurons must be cultured on surfaces coated with poly-L-ornithine (PO) and laminin (use ThermoLife sciences Laminin for neuron differentiation).
 - DPC cultures must be monitored regularly to ensure optimal morphology and density prior to differentiation.
-
- All media should be prepared fresh and only in the amount needed for that day. Excess media may be stored at 4 °C for up to 7 days but it is preferable to use freshly prepared media.
 - DPC cultures must be monitored regularly to ensure optimal morphology and density prior to differentiation.

2 Materials

The quality of materials used in this protocol is critical to its success. The suppliers and catalogue numbers listed in this section allowed for the successful preparation of DPCs expressing dopaminergic progenitor markers. DPCs generated using this protocol can be further differentiated into DNPs expressing dopaminergic neuronal markers. It is important to note that at times there can be significant lot-to-lot variability in the quality of materials which may negatively impact neuronal cultures.

Refer to the product data sheet from the supplier for further details on storage and preparation instructions.

2.1 Labware

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #
Cell scraper	Corning	3010
Conical tube, 15-mL	ThermoFisher	352097
Culture flask, T25	ThermoFisher	12-556-009
Culture flask, T75	ThermoFisher	12-556-010
Culture plate, 24-well	ThermoFisher	087721
Culture plate, 96-well (flat-bottom)	Falcon	353219
Glass coverslip, 12-mm	ThermoFisher	12-545-80
Glass pipette, 5-mL	ThermoFisher	13-678-27E
Glass pipette, 10-mL	ThermoFisher	13-678-26C
Culture dish, 60 mm non-treated	Eppendorf	0030701011
Petri dish, 100 mm	Fisher	FB0875712
Parafilm	ThermoFisher	13-374-12
Plastic serological pipette, 10-mL	Sarstedt	86.1254.001
Plastic serological pipette, 1-mL	Fisher	13-678-11B
Plastic serological pipette, 5-mL	Sarstedt	86.1253.001
Polypropylene microcentrifuge tube	Fisher	02-681-273
EB-Disk 948 ultra-low attachment surface	eNUVIO	enuvio.com
EB-Disk 948 Centrifuge Adapter (double)	eNUVIO	enuvio.com

2.2 Culture reagents

Working aliquots of culture reagents that require storage at 4 °C can be stored for up to two weeks unless otherwise stated.

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #	Stock conc.	Working conc.	Storage temp.
Antibiotic-Antimycotic	Gibco	15240-062	100x	1x	Stock: -20 °C Working: 4 °C
Anti-adherence Rinsing Solution	STEMCELL Technologies	07010	1x	1x	Room temperature
Ascorbic acid	Sigma	A5960	200 mM	200 µM	Stock: -20 °C Working: 4 °C
B27*	Gibco	17504044	50x	1x	Stock: -20 °C Working: 4 °C
BDNF	Peprotech	450-02	20 µg/mL	20 ng/mL	Stock: -20 °C Working: 4 °C
Brainphys Neuronal medium	STEMCELL Technologies	05790	1X	1X	4 °C
CHIR99021	Selleckchem	S2924	3 mM	1 µM; 3 µM	Stock: -80 °C Working: 4 °C
Compound E (γ-secretase inhibitor) *	STEMCELL Technologies	73954	0.1 mM	0.1 µM	Stock: -80 °C Working: 4 °C
db-cAMP	Carbosynth	ND07996	0.5 M	0.5 mM	Stock: -80 °C Working: 4 °C
DMEM/F12	Gibco	10565-018	1x	1x	4 °C
DMSO	Fisher	BP231-1	100%	10%	Room temperature
Ethanol	Greenfield global	26456	100%	70%	Room temperature
FBS	Gibco	12484-028	1x	1x	Stock: -80 °C Working: Room temperature

FGF8b	Peprotech	100-25	100 µg/mL	100 ng/mL	Stock: –80 °C Working: 4 °C
GDNF	Peprotech	450-10	20 µg/mL	20 ng/mL	GDNF
Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent†	STEMCELL Technologies	07174	1x	1x	Room temperature
Laminin	Sigma	L2020	1 mg/mL‡	Culture vessel coating: 5 µg/mL	Stock: –80 °C Working: 4 °C
	Thermo Life Sciences	23017-015			
Matrigel Matrix hESC-qualified (monolayer method)	Corning Millipore	354277	100x	1x	Stock: –80 °C Working: 4 °C§
MEM nonessential amino acid (NEAA) solution	Wisent	321-011-EL	100x	1x	4 °C
mTeSR1 5X supplement	STEMCELL Technologies	05850 (component #05852)	5x	1x	Stock: –20 °C Working: 4 °C
mTeSR1 basal media	STEMCELL Technologies	05850 (component #05851)	1x	1x	4 °C
N2*	Gibco	17502048	100x	1x	Stock: –20 °C Working: 4 °C
N2A Supplement A	STEMCELL Technologies	07152	100X	N2A Supplement A	STEMCELL Technologies
NeuroCult SM1 Neuronal Supplement	STEMCELL Technologies	05711	NeuroCult SM1 Neuronal Supplement	STEMCELL Technologies	05711
Noggin	Peprotech	120-10C	200 µg/mL	200 ng/mL	Stock: –80 °C Working: 4 °C
Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS)	Wisent	311-010-CL	1x	1x	Room temperature

Poly-L-ornithine (PO)	Sigma	P3655	1 mg/mL	10 µg/mL	Stock: -20 °C Working: 4 °C
Purmorphamine§	Sigma	SML-0868	2 mM	2 µM	Stock: -80 °C
SB431542	Selleckchem	S1067	10 mM	10 µM	Stock: -80 °C Working: 4 °C
SHH(C24II)	Peprtech	100-45-500ug	200 µg/mL	200 ng/mL	Stock: -80 °C Working: 4 °C
STEMdiff Neural Progenitor Basal Medium	STEMCELL Technologies	05834	1X	1X	Stock: -20 °C Working: 4 °C
STEMdiff Neural Progenitor Supplement A	STEMCELL Technologies	05836	50X	1X	Stock: -20 °C Working: 4 °C
STEMdiff Neural Progenitor Supplement B	STEMCELL Technologies	05837	1000X	1X	Stock: -20 °C Working: 4 °C
StemPro Accutase Cell Dissociation Reagent	Thermo-Fisher	A1110501	1X	1X	Stock: -20 °C Working: 37 °C
Triton® X-100	Wisent Inc.	TRX506.500	10%	0.1%	Room temperature
Y-27632 (ROCK inhibitor)	Selleckchem	S1049	10 mM	10 µM	Stock: -80 °C Working: 4 °C

*Light-sensitive reagent. Stock and working aliquots should be covered in aluminum foil to minimize exposure to light.

†The incubation time and temperature for Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent may vary depending on cell morphology.

‡Laminin from Thermo Life Sciences is slightly better than laminin from Sigma for culturing neurons for longer than 4 weeks.

‡Laminin stock concentration may vary from batch to batch. The precise concentration is labelled on the tube. Laminin stock solution must be aliquoted into polypropylene microcentrifuge tubes.

§Matrigel working solution must be used immediately or stored at -20°C for later use.

§§The working concentration range of Purmorphamine is very narrow. Prepare the stock solution as accurately as possible. When adding stock solution to culture media, use the smallest tip and a well-calibrated pipette.

2.3 Equipment

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #
Cell counter	Logos Biosystems	LUNA-II Automated cell counter
Cell counting slide	Logos Biosystems	05181401
Cell culture incubator	ThermoFisher Scientific	Steri-Cycle Model 370 Ref#20
Cell culture water bath	FisherScientific	IsoTemp GPD20
Centrifuge	Eppendorf 5702	022626001
Light microscope	Motic	AE2000
LUNA-II Automated cell counter	Logos Biosystems	5181401

3 Protocol

3.1 EB generation

Materials:

- iPSC culture recovered from frozen and passaged at least twice (10-cm dish, 80%–90% confluent)
- Single EB-Disk containing 948 microwells
- 60 mm non-treated culture dish
- 5-mL glass pipette
- 15-mL tubes
- DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic
- Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent
- Y-27632 (ROCK inhibitor)
- Media:

Table 1. iPSC and DA EB media: composition and preparation.

Media	Components
mTeSR1	<p>Preparation instructions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Thaw mTeSR1 5x supplement at 4 °C overnight.• Add 100 mL of mTeSR1 5x supplement to 400 mL mTeSR1 basal media to obtain 500 mL of complete media. Mix well.• Complete media is ready for use and does not require filtering. However, the complete media can be filtered using a 0.2-µm low protein-binding filter.• Warm complete media at room temperature (do not warm at 37 °C). <p>Storage instructions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Once supplement is thawed, use immediately or store at 4 °C for up to 2 days.• Complete media is stable when stored at 4°C for up to 2 weeks or at –20 °C for up to 6 months. Prepare 40-mL aliquots in 50-mL conical tubes, seal with Parafilm, and store at –20 °C. Thaw aliquots overnight at 4 °C (do not warm in a 37 °C water bath). Do not refreeze aliquots after thawing.
DA EB media	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• DMEM/F12• 1x N2• 1x B27• 1x MEM NEAA solution• 200 ng/mL Noggin• 200 ng/mL SHH (C24II)• 1 µM CHIR99021• 10 µM SB431542• 100 ng/mL FGF8b

- Centrifuge
- 37 °C/5% CO₂ cell culture incubator

Procedure:

1. At Day 0, assess iPSC culture to ensure that it is 80% to 90% confluent, cells are tightly packed with smooth edges, and there is little to no spontaneous differentiation. Remove all regions of spontaneous differentiation before starting the procedure. To learn how to remove spontaneous differentiation refer to our [iPSC culture protocol](#) or watch our [iPSC culture instructional video](#).
 - Never use iPSCs just recovered from a thaw to start the induction. Thawed iPSCs should be passaged at least twice prior to DA NPC induction. Keep in mind that high-quality iPSCs are essential for neuronal induction. Please review the criteria for high-quality cultures by watching our instructional video "[Assessing iPSC Morphology](#)."
2. Before starting the cell seeding protocol, prepare EB disks by placing one disk per sterile 6 cm non-treated dish with a sterile forceps. Make sure to place the disk with the wells facing up.
3. Add 6–8 mL of anti-adherence solution to the disk and press the disk down into the dish with sterile tweezers to eliminate as many air bubbles as possible.
4. Centrifuge the disk for 5 min at 1200 rpm in a swinging bucket rotor fitted with plate holders to remove all remaining air bubbles in the well. Place the disk inside the biosafety cabinet and leave it undisturbed until you are ready to plate the cells on it.
5. Aspirate media from the iPSC culture dish and rinse with 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic.
6. Add 5 mL Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent and incubate at 37 °C for 4 to 6 minutes.
 - If culture is more than 80% confluent or if the colonies are too large or tightly packed, extend incubation time in Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent to 5 to 7 minutes.
7. Aspirate the Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent and wash the cells with 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic.
8. Add 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic to cells and gently detach the colonies with a cell scraper.
 - If cells have already detached from the dish, add 5 mL DMEM/F12 directly to the dish without aspirating the Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent, then gently detach the remaining colonies with a cell scraper.
 - Cells are rinsed to remove dying cells and residual Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent from the dish.
9. Transfer the cell suspension to a 15-mL conical tube. Rinse the dish with an additional 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic to collect any remaining cells and transfer to a fresh tube.
10. Pellet cells by centrifuging at 1200 rpm (200 g) for 3 minutes.

11. Remove supernatant and resuspend cells in 800 μ L DA EB media with 10 μ M of Rock inhibitor.
12. Create a single cell suspension to count the cells by pipetting:
 - a. Three times with a P1000 tip
 - b. Two times with a P200 tip attached to a P1000 tip
 - Do not over-pipette the cells as they are sensitive to shear forces.
 - Use a P1000 pipette in both cases.
13. Transfer 10 μ L of cell suspension into 90 μ L DMEM/F12/0.5 mL Eppendorf. Mix well. Add 10 μ L of 1:10 diluted cell suspension into 10 μ L of Trypan blue (0.4% STEMCELL Technologies #07050). Place 10 μ L of Trypan blue-cell mix into the cell counter slide. Count three cell fields with a LUNA-II Automated cell counter (or another one if different one available), take the average of cell number, and calculate the volume needed to plate the number of cells desired. *Please note that other counting methods can also be used.*
14. By aspiration, remove as much as possible of the anti-adherent solution from the disk.
 - IMPORTANT: Do not aspirate directly from the disk. Aspirate from a corner of the dish without touching the wells of the disk to avoid making bubbles in the wells.
15. Rinse the disk three times with DMEM/F12
 - Press disk down into the dish with sterile 200 μ L tips once you add the media to make sure the media goes inside the wells and bottom.
16. Rinse the disk one more time with DA EB media to equilibrium EB-Disk.
17. Remove the DA EB media as much as possible without disturbing the microwells.
18. Dilute 10 million iPSCs in 1.5 mL of DA EB media.
19. Pipette 0.75 mL of cell suspension around the edges of the EB-Disk and then rest of cell suspension directly into the middle of the disk, where the platform is.
20. Place the dish into the centrifuge adapter and spin it at 1200 rpm for 10 min to allow cells to settle onto the wells of the EB-Disk. *To learn more about this step, please watch our [EB-disk protocol instructional video](#).*
21. Bring the dish to the biosafety cabinet and fill up the dish by adding up to 7 mL of DA EB media. The media should cover the EBs.
 - IMPORTANT: Do not pipet directly on the microwells. Media should be added to the side of the disk to not disturb the EBs.
22. Change the media every 2 days using an 80% media change. Monitor cultures for EB formation.
 - DO NOT aspirate media directly from the microwells, aspirate it from the side of the dish instead.
 - Gently add 6–7 mL of DA EB media without ROCK inhibitor to the side of the dish.
 - Return dish to the incubator.

- If the media turns yellow, change media daily.
- Examples of DA EBs at various days in culture are shown in Figure 4.

EB generation

Figure 5. Bright-field phase contrast of AIW002-02 DA EBs at days 2 to 7 (4x objective).

3.2 Rosette formation and dissociation

Materials:

- DA-EBs in 948 microwells EB-Disk
- Matrigel coated T25 flask
- 10-mL glass pipette
- 100 mm Petri dish
- 15-mL tubes
- DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic
- Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent
- Y-27632 (ROCK inhibitor)
- Poly-ornithine/laminin coated T75 flask
- Media:

Table 2. DA induction media: composition and preparation.

Media	Components
DA induction media	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• DMEM/F12• 1x N2• 1x B27• 1x MEM NEAA solution• 200 ng/mL Noggin• 200 ng/mL SHH (C24II)• 3 μM CHIR99021• 10 μM SB431542• 100 ng/mL FGF8b

1. At day 7, using an autoclaved metal forceps, delicately transfer the EB-Disk to a 100 mm Petri dish containing 15 mL of DMEM/F12 with 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic. Place the disk with the microwells facing downwards.
2. Gently agitate the disk with the metal forceps, several EBs should float out into the medium. Then transfer EBs with a 10 mL glass pipette to 50 mL tube.
3. Repeat **step 2** twice until no more EBs remain in the disk or the media.
4. Allow EBs to sediment to the bottom of the tube by gravity. Remove supernatant by aspirating as close to the EB pellet as possible without disturbing them. Gently resuspend cells with 2 mL of DA induction media containing ROCK inhibitor (2 μ M).
5. Transfer 1 mL of EB suspension each into two of Matrigel-coated T25 containing 4 mL of DA induction medium. Move the flasks in several back-and-forth and side-to-side motions to distribute the EBs. Incubate the cells at 37 °C.
6. At day 9, change the media to DA induction media without ROCK inhibitor. Continue to change media every two days.
 - If the media turns yellow, change media daily.

- Rosettes typically appear 2–3 days after re-plating the EBs on Matrigel-coated flasks (Day 11). An example of DA rosettes 4 days after re-plating is shown in **Figure 5**.

Rosette formation

Figure 6. Bright-field phase contrast of AIW002-02 DA rosettes formation. (Top: 4x objective; bottom: 10x objective).

- The morphology of rosettes can vary between cell lines. Examples of DA rosettes from different cell lines are shown in **Figure 6**.

Figure 7. Bright-field phase contrast of the formation of DA rosettes varies between cell lines. (Top: 4x objective; bottom: 10x objective, 4 days after re-plating).

7. On Day 14, aspirate media from rosettes and rinse with 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic. Add 2 mL Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent and incubate at room temperature for 5 minutes.
 - Do not incubate rosettes in Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent at 37 °C because this will cause all the cells to detach, including non-desirable cell types on the bottom or the edge of rosettes.
8. Tap the side of the flask forcefully with the palm of your hand three to six times to detach the rosettes from the flask. Without removing the Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent, add 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic and transfer rosettes to a 15-mL conical tube. Rinse the flask with an additional 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic to collect any remaining rosettes and transfer to the tube. Pellet cells by centrifuging at 1200 rpm (200 g) for 3 minutes.
 - Following dissociation of the rosettes, undesired cells will remain attached to the flask (Figure 7).

Rosette dissociation

Figure 8. Bright-field phase contrast of undesired cells remaining on flask after dissociation of AIW002-02 DA rosettes (left: T25 flask after rosettes dissociation, middle: 4x objective; right: 10x objective).

9. Remove the supernatant and resuspend rosettes in 1 mL DA induction media. Pipette up and down 2–3 times to break up the rosettes into small cell aggregates.
 - Do not over-pipette the rosettes into a single-cell suspension. Larger cell aggregates or single cells will not differentiate well into NPCs.
10. Transfer cell aggregates to a PO/laminin coated T25 or T75 flask and add 4 mL or 14 mL, respectively, of DA induction media. Incubate rosettes at 37 °C.
 - The number and size of flasks to use are determined by the size of the cell pellet retrieved in the 15 mL centrifuge tube (**Table 3**).

Table 3. Number and size of flasks to use based on cell pellet size.

Pellet size	Number/size of flasks
<2 mm	One T25 flask
2–3 mm	Two T25 flasks
3–4 mm	One T75 flask
>4 mm	One T75 flask + one T25 flask

- For rosettes plated in DA-induction media A, label cultures as P0.
11. Change the media every 2 days until Day 21 and then proceed to **Section 3.3**.
 - If the media turns yellow, change media daily.
 - An example of DPCs 1 day after plating rosettes (Day 15) is shown in **Figure 8**.

Figure 9. Bright-field phase contrast of AIW002-02 DPCs 1 day after plating rosettes (Day 15).

3.3 Expansion, cryopreservation of DPCs

Materials:

- DPC culture at Day 21
- 15-mL tube
- DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic
- Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent
- 10% DMSO in FBS
- Media:

Table 4. DPC media composition.

Media	Components
DPC media	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• DMEM/F12• 1x N2• 1x B27• 1x MEM NEAA solution• 200 μM Ascorbic acid (optional)• 20 ng/mL BDNF (optional)

Procedure:

1. At day 21, aspirate media and rinse with 5 mL or 10 mL (T25 or T75 flask) of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic. Add 2 mL or 7 mL (T25 or T75 flask) Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent and incubate at 37 °C for 5 minutes.
2. Tap the side of the flask with the palm of your hand three to six times to detach the cells from the flask. Without removing the Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent, add 5 mL or 8 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic and transfer NPCs to a 15-mL conical tube. Rinse the flask with an additional 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic to collect any remaining cells and transfer to the tube. Pellet cells by centrifuging at 1200 rpm (200 g) for 3 minutes.
3. Remove the supernatant and resuspend cells in the appropriate media according to the recommendations for expansion, cryopreservation, or final neuron differentiation outlined in **Table 5**.

Table 5. Recommendations for expansion, cryopreservation, or differentiation.

Application	Recommendations
Expansion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resuspend and plate cells in NPC media on a PO/laminin-coated T75 flask (label cultures as P1). • Change media every two days, or daily if the media turns yellow. • Split cells once per week (see Table 3 for plating recommendations based on pellet size). Do not passage more than once per week, even if culture is over-confluent. • If cells are at low density or do not proliferate well, ascorbic acid and BDNF may be added to the media at a final concentration to stimulate cell growth.
Cryopreservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freeze cultures at P0 in FBS containing 10% DMSO. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Label cryovials with NPC type, passage number, induction time and induction date (DPC P0, 3W EB 4/15/2022).

- DPCs can be kept in culture until they are ready for differentiation. DPC cultures must meet specific criteria in terms of morphology and density before they can be differentiated into neurons.
- The examples of different passages DPCs (3-week induction) 1 day after splitting are shown in **Figure 9**.

Figure 10. Bright-field phase contrast images of AIW002-02 DPCs being expanded across three passages (3-week induction) 1 day after splitting.

3.4 Coating plates for DPC expansion phase

Materials:

- T25 flasks
- PO (1 mg/mL)
- Laminin (1 mg/mL)
- 1x PBS
- DMEM/F12
- Antibiotic-Antimycotic
- 37 °C/5% CO₂ cell culture incubator

Procedure:

1. Prepare PO working solution by adding 500 µL of PO stock solution to 50 mL 1x PBS.
 - Thaw PO stock solution at 4°C.
 - Ensure transfer of all PO stock solution by rinsing tube with PBS twice.
 - PO working solution can be stored at 4°C for up to two months.
2. Apply 3 mL PO solution to each T25 flask and swirl to spread across surfaces.
 - **IMPORTANT:** Ensure culture surfaces are coated completely and evenly. Do not let surfaces dry. Uneven coating or evaporation of coating may affect cell distribution.
3. Incubate culture vessel at 37 °C for at least 2 hours or overnight.
4. Aspirate PO solution from culture vessel and wash surfaces three times with 5 mL 1x PBS.
5. Prepare Sigma laminin working solution by adding 100 µL of laminin stock solution and 200 µL of Antibiotic-Antimycotic to 20 mL of cold DMEM/F12.
 - **IMPORTANT:** Store laminin stock solution at –80 °C and thaw at 4°C before using. At room temperature laminin can adsorb to plastic and aggregate.
 - Laminin working solution can be stored at 4°C for up to two weeks.
6. Apply 3 mL Sigma laminin solution to each T25 flask and swirl to spread across surfaces.
 - **IMPORTANT:** Ensure culture surfaces are coated completely and evenly. Do not let surfaces dry. Uneven coating or evaporation of coating may affect cell distribution.
7. Incubate culture vessel at 37 °C for a minimum of two hours.
8. If plating cells on culture vessel immediately, aspirate laminin solution and proceed with plating. If not plating cells on culture vessel immediately, do not aspirate laminin solution and store culture vessel in a 37 °C incubator for up to 3 days.
 - **IMPORTANT:** If using PO/laminin-coated culture vessels that have been stored (i.e., if not using immediately after coating procedure), check quality of coating before plating cells. Uneven coating or evaporation of coating may affect cell distribution.

3.5 Thawing and culturing DPCs

Materials:

- Frozen cryovial of DPCs (refer to SOP [EDDU-008-02](#) for DPC induction)
- PO/laminin coated T25 flasks
- 15-mL conical tubes
- DMEM/F12
- Y-27632 (ROCK inhibitor)
- DPC culture media: STEMdiff Neural Progenitor Basal Medium + STEMdiff Neural Progenitor Supplement A (50X) + STEMdiff Neural Progenitor Supplement B (1000X) + Purmorphamine 2 μ M
- 37 °C cell culture water bath
- 37 °C/5% CO₂ cell culture incubator
- Centrifuge
- Light microscope

Procedure:

1. Prepare DPC medium.
 - Thaw a bottle of STEMdiff Neural Progenitor Basal Medium at 4°C overnight until it is completely defrosted. Divide the Basal Medium into 40 mL aliquots using 50 mL sterile Falcon tubes. On the day of medium preparation, thaw STEMdiff Neural Progenitor Supplement A (50X) and STEMdiff Neural Progenitor Supplement B (1000X) on ice. Divide Supplement A into 800 μ l aliquots and Supplement B into 40 μ l aliquots. All the aliquots should be stored at -20 °C for long-term maintenance until the expiration date provided by manufacture.
 - Thaw a tube of Basal Medium aliquot at 4°C overnight and thaw Supplement A and B aliquots on ice. Warm up Purmorphamine at room temperature. Add all the supplements into Basal Medium, mix well and this medium will be kept as DPC media for culture.
 - DPC media can be stored at 4°C up to two weeks. Warm up DPC media at room temperature before usage. Warming up DA NPC media at 37 °C is not recommended.
2. Thaw a frozen cryovial of DPCs in 37 °C water bath.
 - Transfer the frozen cryovial from liquid nitrogen tank in small liquid nitrogen transfer vessel or dry ice.
 - Thaw cryovial quickly in a water bath.
 - After cells have thawed, sterilize the outside of the cryovial with 70% ethanol.
3. Transfer cells to a 15-mL conical tube containing 5 mL DMEM/F12 and resuspend. Pellet cells by centrifuging tube at 1200 rpm (200 g) for 3 minutes.

4. Remove supernatant. Carefully resuspend the cell pellet in 5 mL of DPC media and transfer entire cell suspension to a PO/laminin-coated flask. Add ROCK inhibitor to media (1:1000). Incubate cells at 37 °C.
 - T25 flasks are recommended for growing DPCs to maintain an ideal density. The optimal density for recovery from a frozen stock is 1.5 million to 2 million cells per T25 flask.
 - The number and size of flasks to use are determined by the size of the cell pellet (**Table 6**).

Table 6. Number and size of flasks to use based on cell pellet size.

Pellet size	Number/size of flasks
< 1 mm	Thaw an additional cryovial of DPCs and add cells from both cryovials together on one T25 flask
1–1.5 mm	One T25 flask

5. After 24 hours, assess cell morphology and density (refer to **Table 7**). Change media every other day or when it becomes yellow. Allow DPCs to recover for at least 1 week before plating.

Table 7. DPC culture examples.

Image	Comments	Suggestion
<p>AIW2-2 DPC in a T25 one day after thawing</p>	Example of a typical DPC culture with good morphology and density.	Keep in culture until ready for plating.

<p>Magnified images from above</p>	<p>Same as above.</p>	<p>Same as above.</p>
<p>SNCA-triplication DPCs in a T25 culture 8 days after thawing</p>	<p>Example of DPCs with good morphology and ready for plating.</p>	<p>Proceed plating within three days.</p>
<p>Magnified images from above</p>	<p>Same as above.</p>	<p>Same as above.</p>

<p>Parkin KO-XCL DPCs one day after thawing.</p>	<p>Very low survival rate after thawing. Most cells died.</p>	<p>Discard culture and thaw another vial of frozen stock.</p>
<p>AIW2-2 DPCs cultured in a T25.</p>	<p>Low density and low proportion of DPCs (>30% non neuronal cells)</p>	<p>Not recommended to use for differentiation and screens.</p>
<p>Synuclein KO/AIW2-2 DPCs in a T25 culture seven days after thawing.</p>	<p>Good density and most of the cells are pre-neuronal DPCs and starting to form clusters.</p>	<p>Proceed plating as soon as possible (within two days). Incubate the cells with accutase for six minutes at 37 °C and pipette them gently.</p>
	<p>Example of a low confluence culture with certain amount of pre-neuronal cells. Cells form mash-like structures and may lift easily.</p>	<p>Culture can be kept for no more than three days. Pipette gently and carefully when changing medium.</p>

<p>AIW2-2 DPCs in a T25 culture five days after thawing.</p>		
<p>AIW2-2 DPCs cultured in a T25 flask.</p>	<p>Good density but very low proportion of DPCs (<5%).</p>	<p>Terminate culture and discard.</p>

3.6 Automated Coating of 96-well plates

Materials:

- 1 µg/mL PLO in PBS
- 5 µg/mL laminin in DMEM/F12
- DMEM/F12
- 0.1% Triton in PBS
- 1X PBS
- dH₂O
- ddH₂O
- 70% ethanol
- 96-well plates (black/clear flat bottom)

Equipment:

- EL406 Washer Dispenser
- 10 µL cassette
- Liquid Handling Control Software

Notes:

- Refer to [EDDU-016-01](#) for information on the usage of EL406 Washer Dispenser.
- Plan to coat 96-well plates with PLO the day before cell seeding.
- Plates should be fully coated, and the plate washer should be ready for cell seeding before starting DPC detachment and suspension to minimize the time in suspension.
- This protocol is specific for the EL406 washer dispenser that we have available for our protocol but be aware that coating and plating can vary between different washers and dispensers.

Procedure:

1. Turn ON the EL406 Washer Dispenser and open the Liquid Handling Control Software.
2. Spray the surface of the BSLII cabinet and the EL406 Washer Dispenser with 70% ethanol.
3. Spray the cassette with 70% ethanol before placing it in the EL406 Washer Dispenser (**Figure 12A** shows cassette position for dispensing).
4. Place the cassette lines into 70% EtOH and under the folder '1-PLO Coating' select the program '1-Sterilize 10 µL cassette with 70% EtOH' to sterilize the cassette by priming with 70% ethanol. See **Figure 11** for an example of the program interface.

- Ensure the washer bottles are filled with appropriate solutions before using the machine. If any bottle needs refilling it should be done before the sterilization steps.

Figure 11. Screenshot of path and folder structure for PLO coating in black 96-well plates.

- Place the cassette in a ‘relaxed’ position to empty the lines by gravity (**Figure 12B**)
- Allow enough time for the ethanol to evaporate before using the machine.

Figure 12. Cassette positions in EL406. A) Tubing under tension, ready for dispensing. B) “Relaxed” position to release tension and allow outflow by gravity.

- Place the cassette lines into PLO (dead volume of 15 mL + 5% volume needed, **Table 8**) and select the program ‘2-Prime 10 μ L cassette with PLO’ to prime the cassette with PLO.

Table 8. Recommended volumes of PO or laminin working solutions based on the number of plates.

Number of 96-well plates	Volume needed	Volume to prepare
4	20 mL	36 mL
5	25 mL	41.25 mL
6	30 mL	46.5 mL
7	35 mL	51.75 mL
8	40 mL	57 mL
9	45 mL	62.25 mL
10	50 mL	67.5 mL

- Place 96-well plate on plate carrier (remove the lid), oriented with the A1 well to the back-left corner of the carrier.
 - Select the program '3-96-well plate PLO coating' to dispense 50 µL of PLO per well.
 - Put plates in the incubator for overnight incubation at 37 °C.
 - Place cassette lines at the top of the PLO container and select the program '4-Purge PLO' to purge the PLO from the cassette.
 - Placing the lines at the top of the container will decrease the number of bubbles formed in the solution.
 - Select the program '5-Clean 10 µL cassette' to clean the cassette with 0.1% Triton, PBS, ddH₂O, and 70% ethanol, in that order.
 - The lines are rinsed with ddH₂O above a waste container before being placed into each cleaning solution.
 - Place the cassette in a 'relaxed' position.
 - Turn OFF the EL406 Washer Dispenser and close the Liquid Handling Control Software.
1. After overnight PLO coating, turn ON the EL406 Washer Dispenser and open the Liquid Handling Control Software.
 - Spray the surface of the BSLII cabinet, the EL406 washer, and the cassette with 70% ethanol.
 2. Place the cassette lines into 70% EtOH and under the folder '2-Wash PLO & add laminin' select the program '1-Sterilize washer and 10 µL cassette with 70% EtOH' to sterilize the washer and the cassette by priming with 70% ethanol (**Figure 13**). Ensure the washer bottles are filled with appropriate solutions before using the machine. If any bottle needs refilling it should be done before the sterilization steps.

Figure 13. Screenshot of path and folder structure for wash PLO and laminin coating in black 96-well plates

- Run one cycle for EtOH dry and select the program '2-Run EtOH dry' and place the cassette in a 'relaxed' position to empty the lines by gravity. Allow enough time for the ethanol to evaporate before using the machine.
- Place the cassette lines into DMEM/F12 and select the program '3-Prime 10 μ L cassette with DMEM' to remove any remaining ethanol before priming with laminin.
- Place the cassettes lines into laminin and select the program '4-Prime 10 μ L cassette with laminin and Syringe B' to prime the cassette with laminin and to remove any air bubbles in the Syringe B line that might have resulted due to evaporation.
- Select the program '5-wash PLO + add laminin' to aspirate PLO, then wash twice with 50 μ L of ddH₂O, and dispense 50 μ L of laminin per well.
- Incubate plates at 37 °C for at least 2 h.
- Place cassette lines at the top of the laminin container (recommended volume see Table 3) and select the program '6-Purge laminin' to purge the laminin from the cassette and select the program '7-clean 10 μ l cassette' to clean the cassette with 0.1% Triton, PBS, ddH₂O, and 70% ethanol, in that order.
- The lines are rinsed with ddH₂O above a waste container before being placed into each cleaning solution.
- Place the cassette in a 'relaxed' position.
- Turn OFF the EL406 Washer Dispenser and close the Liquid Handling Control Software.

3.7 Plating DPCs into 96-well plates

Materials:

- DA in T25 flask
- PO/laminin-coated 96-well plates
- 15-mL conical tubes
- DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic
- StemPro Accutase Cell Dissociation Reagent
- Y-27632 (ROCK inhibitor)
- Plating media: DMEM/F12 + B27 + N2 + Y-27632 (ROCK inhibitor)

Equipment:

- 37 °C cell culture water bath
- 37 °C/5% CO₂ cell culture incubator
- Centrifuge
- Light microscope
- Cell counter and cell counting slide
- EL406 Washer Dispenser
- 10 µL cassette
- Liquid Handling Control Software

Notes:

- Prior to seeding, DPCs are cultured and expanded in PLO/ laminin coated T25 flasks.
- Make sure 96-well plates are properly coated prior to start processing cells.
- For an individual 96-well plate, 1.5×10^6 DA NPCs are required (15,000 cells/ well). Plan cell culture accordingly to obtain enough cells (refer to **Table 9** for total number of cells needed for plating). Normally, $1.5 \sim 3 \times 10^7$ DPCs can be obtained from one confluent T25 flask.
- Low passage DPCs are preferable (Using cells from the initial thawing flask is highly recommended if purity of the culture is crucial for downstream experiments. DPCs can be passed for up to two passages according to the morphology of the culture). (See **Table 7**)

Procedure:

1. Rinse cells once with DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic.
2. Add 3 mL of pre-warmed StemPro Accutase Cell Dissociation Reagent to the cells and incubate at 37 °C for 5 minutes until the cells detach. Stop cell dissociation by adding 5 mL DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic. Transfer cells to a 15-mL conical tube. Rinse flask with 5 mL DMEM/F12 and transfer to the tube containing the cells. Pellet cells by centrifuging at 1400 rpm for 3 minutes.

- The activity of StemPro Accutase Cell Dissociation Reagent may decrease over time at 4°C (storage of leftover reagent).
3. Resuspend cells carefully in 1 mL plating media using a 200 µL tip on top of a 1000 µL tip to obtain a single-cell suspension.
 - Do not over-pipette the suspension as this will destroy the premature neurons.
 - Resuspension technique varies depending on NPC morphology and cell density, and the activity of StemPro Accutase Cell Dissociation Reagent.
 4. Add 3 mL plating media into the single-cell suspension and determine cell number using cell counter. Dilute NPCs in plating media in appropriate vessel (50 mL Falcon tubes or sterile glass bottles for higher volumes), final concentration should be 150,000 cells/mL (15,000 cells/well). Prepare enough diluted cell suspension for plating all the 96-well plates (see **Table 9**): volume needed (10 mL cell suspension per 96-well plate) + dead volume of 15 mL + 5% volume needed. It is important to keep cells in suspension for as short a time as possible. Before seeding, swirl vessel containing cells before dispensing to prevent settling and clumping of NPCs.

Table 9. Recommended volumes of cell suspension to prepare based on the number of plates.

Number of 96-well plates	Volume of cell suspension required	Volume of cell suspension to be prepared	Total number of cells needed
4	40 mL	57 mL	8.55 million
5	50 mL	67.5 mL	10.125 million
6	60 mL	78 mL	11.7 million
7	70 mL	88.5 mL	13.275 million
8	80 mL	99 mL	14.85 million
9	90 mL	109.5 mL	16.425 million
10	100 mL	120 mL	18 million

5. Turn ON the EL406 Washer Dispenser and open the Liquid Handling Control Software.
6. Spray the surface of the BSLII cabinet and the EL406 Washer Dispenser with 70% ethanol.
7. Spray the cassette with 70% ethanol before placing it in the EL406 Washer Dispenser.
8. Under the folder 'Seed cells' select the program '1-sterilize washer and 10 µL cassette' to sterilize the washer and the cassette by priming with 70% ethanol. (See **Figure 14**)

- Run one cycle for EtOH dry and select the program '2-Run EtOH dry' and place the cassette in a 'relaxed' position to empty the lines by gravity. Allow enough time for the ethanol to evaporate before using the machine.
- Place the cassette lines into DMEM/F12 and select the program '3-Prime 10 μ L cassette with DMEM/F12.
- Place the cassette lines into NPC media and select the program '4-Prime 10 μ L cassette with cells' to prime the cassette with NPCs.
- Select the program '5-96-well plate aspirate laminin and seed cells' to aspirate the laminin and dispense 100 μ L of NPCs per well. The cell density will be 15,000 cells/well.
- Put plates back into incubator.
- Place the cassette lines at the top of the cell suspension container and select the program '9-Purge cells' to purge the cell suspension from the cassette.
- Select the program '10-Clean 10 μ L cassette' to clean the cassette with 0.1% Triton, PBS, ddH₂O, and 70% ethanol, in that order.
- Place the cassette in a 'relaxed' position to empty the lines by gravity.
- Select the program 'Wash with PBS, H₂O, EtOH' to clean the washer with PBS, ddH₂O, and 70% ethanol, in that order.
- Remove the cassette from the EL406 Washer Dispenser and store in its appropriate box.
- Turn OFF the EL406 Washer Dispenser and close the Liquid Handling Control Software.

Figure 14. Screenshot of path and folder structure for DPC seeding in black 96-well plates.

3.8 Differentiation and maintenance of DA neurons in 96-well plates

Materials:

- 96-well plates with DPC
- DA differentiation media

Component	Final concentration
BrainPhys Neuronal Medium	
NeuroCult SM1 Neuronal Supplement	1x
N2 Supplement-A	1x
BDNF	20 ng/mL
GDNF	20 ng/mL
AA	200 µM
db-cAMP	0.5 mM
Compound E	0.1 µM
Laminin (Sigma)	1 µg/mL

Equipment:

- 37 °C cell culture water bath
- 37 °C/5% CO₂ cell culture incubator
- Light microscope
- Cell counter and cell counting slide
- EL406 Washer Dispenser
- 10 µL cassette
- Liquid Handling Control Software

Notes:

- Prior to start differentiation, assess cell morphology and growing status. Only healthy cultures are recommended to be differentiated.
- BrainPhys Neuronal Media and its supplements NeuroCult SM1 Neuronal Supplement and N2 Supplement-A (STEMCELL Technologies) are used in the current protocol. However, this protocol can be applied with Neurobasal Media (Gibco) and N2 and B27 supplements from Gibco. Prepare DA differentiation media as follows:

Component	Final concentration
Neurobasal™ Medium	
B-27® Supplement	1x
N-2 Supplement	1x
BDNF	20 ng/mL
GDNF	20 ng/mL
AA	200 µM
db-cAMP	0.5 mM
Compound E	0.1 µM
Laminin (sigma)	1 µg/mL

Procedure:

1. Prepare differentiation media. Thaw SM1 and N2A on ice and divide SM1 into 1 mL aliquots and N2A into 500 µL aliquots. Keep these aliquots at -20 °C for long-term preservation. Thaw aliquots of SM1 and N2A. Add one aliquot of SM1 and N2A to 50 mL BrainPhys Neuronal Media. This can be kept as BrainPhys complete media and stored at 4°C up to two weeks. When preparing DA differentiation media, take out the required amount of BrainPhys complete media and warm up at room temperature and add the other supplements fresh before starting DA differentiation. 100 µL of DA differentiation media is required for each well, meaning that 10 mL media is required for one 96-well plate culture. Prepare at least an additional 15 mL for dead volume plus 5% of the volume needed when using the EL406 Windshield Washer Dispenser and Fluid Manager for the process. If changing the medium manually, preparing 20% extra media is recommended. (Medium volume recommendation is shown in **Table 10**.)

Table 10. Recommended volumes of differentiation medium to prepare based on the number of plates.

Number of 96-well plates	Estimated volume needed when using EL406	Estimated volume needed when proceeding manually
2	36 mL	24 mL
3	46.5 mL	36 mL
4	57 mL	48 mL
5	67.5 mL	60 mL
6	78 mL	72 mL
7	88.5 mL	84 mL
8	99 mL	96 mL
9	109.5 mL	108 mL
10	120 mL	120 mL

2. Twenty-four hours after DPCs are plated into 96-well plates, check the cell morphology (**Table 11**) and start differentiation by taking out 50 μ L of the plating media and adding 100 μ L DA differentiation media as following steps:
 - Turn ON the EL406 Washer Dispenser and open the Liquid Handling Control Software.
 - Spray the surface of the BSLII cabinet and the EL406 Washer Dispenser with 70% ethanol.
 - Spray the cassette with 70% ethanol before placing it in the EL406 Washer Dispenser.

3. Under the folder 'Half media change' select the program '1-Sterilize washer and 10 μ L cassette' to sterilize the washer and the cassette by priming with 70% ethanol and place the cassette lines into 70% EtOH (**Figure 15**)
 - Place the cassette in a 'relaxed' position to empty the lines by gravity. Allow enough time for the ethanol to evaporate before using the machine.
 - Run one cycle for EtOH dry and select the program '2-Run EtOH dry.'
 - Run one cycle to rinse EtOH with ddH₂O and select the program '3-Run ddH₂O.'
 - Place the cassette lines into DA differentiation media and select the program '4-prime 10 μ L cassette with media' to prime with DA differentiation media.
 - Place 96-well plate on plate carrier (remove the lid), oriented with the A1 well to the back-left corner of the carrier.
 - Select the program '5-aspirate 50 μ L + dispense 100 μ L' to remove 50 μ L of plating media and add 100 μ L of DA differentiation media per well.
 - Put plates back to incubator to keep culture.

- Select the program 'Clean 10 μ L cassette' to clean the cassette with 0.1% Triton, PBS, ddH₂O, and 70% ethanol, in that order. The lines are rinsed with ddH₂O above a waste container before being placed into each cleaning solution.
- Place the cassette in a 'relaxed' position.
- Turn OFF the EL406 Washer Dispenser and close the Liquid Handling Control Software.
- DA neurons can be cultured in the incubator under current condition up to two weeks without any medium change.

Figure 15. Screenshot of path and folder structure for media change in black 96-well plates.

4. Maintain DA neurons for long-term culture (longer than two weeks).

- After two weeks of differentiation, monitor DA neuron condition under the microscope. If DA neurons are in good condition and need to be kept for long-term differentiation. Prepare DA differentiation media as described above.
- DA neurons tend to detach easily after two-week differentiation. Replenishing media manually is recommended for the neurons at this stage.
- To change the media, carefully remove 50 μ L culture medium from each well and add 50 μ L fresh pre-warmed DA differentiation media into each well. Put plate back into incubator and keep culture. Be very careful and gentle when removing culture media and apply new media onto differentiated DA neurons as cells tends to be detached easily.
- Keep monitoring DA neurons until required for assays. Perform 50 μ L culture medium change once per week or two weeks depending on culture conditions. DA neurons cultured under such condition can last up to six to eight weeks.

Table 11. Cell culture in 96-well plate examples.

Image	Comments	Suggestion
<p data-bbox="204 716 570 827">SNCA-triplication DPCs in a 96-well plate one day after plating.</p>	<p data-bbox="618 302 984 413">Good morphology and good density. Most of the cells (>80%) have neurites.</p>	<p data-bbox="1032 302 1325 373">Start differentiation for downstream assays.</p>
<p data-bbox="204 1339 589 1451">SNCA-triplication DA neurons in a 96-well plate two weeks after differentiation.</p>	<p data-bbox="618 926 984 1037">Good morphology and good density. Most of the cells (>90%) have long neurites.</p>	<p data-bbox="1032 926 1406 997">Keep culture or use the cells for assays.</p>

	<p>Good morphology and good density. Most of the cells (>80%) have neurites.</p>	<p>Start differentiation for downstream assays.</p>
	<p>Good morphology and slightly higher density. Most of the cells (>80%) have neurites.</p>	<p>Start differentiation for downstream assays. Need to monitor morphology as clusters may form after a certain time of differentiation.</p>
	<p>Density is too high. Most of the cells (>70%) have neurites.</p>	<p>Use with cautions. Try to use these cells for NPC related experiments or short-term differentiation. Cells may form clusters or over grow with long-term differentiation.</p>

<p>Synuclein KO/AIW2-2 DPCs in a 96-well plate one day after plating.</p>		
<p>AIW2-2 DPCs in a 96-well plate one day after plating.</p>	<p>Bad morphology. Very low portion (<10%) of cells are with visible neurites.</p>	<p>Not recommend using these cells for any experiment.</p>